

ADDRESSING TO COMMUNICATION BEHAVIOUR IN TEACHING LINGUACULTUROLOGY

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Abstract: Nowadays, in teaching foreign languages, applying for students' communicational behavior is one of the most important duties, which teachers should have. In this modern and developing world, learning the language within its culture and form abilities related to cultural and social aspects of life simultaneously is becoming more essential. When teaching the students, it is necessary to note cross-cultural interference, which may pose barrier to students in the manner of communication. One of the main purposes of the research is how to address to communication behavior in teaching lingua- culturology.

Keywords: Communication, students, teachers, education, skills, non-verbal, verbal

Introduction

It is well known that every nation has its own culture, customs, as well as certain etiquette norms when engaging in communication between teacher and student. Communication can be defined as a way of transferring thoughts and ideas to other people. Communication can either be verbal or non-verbal. Both ways of communication are very important for transferring thoughts. Teachers and students relation stand on the verbal and non-verbal means of communication.

Communication is the blood of success in every walk of life. Effective communication plays an important role in building up the character and standard of student's education. Teacher's skills and ways of communication motivate the students to increase their ability in the field of education. Love, affection, sincerity, obligation, responsibility and dedication from the teacher may bring the prosperity and love which students require towards education. A positive relation between teachers and students creates a healthy environment for good education. University is the stage where sensible and mature students obtain admission to grow their professional skills. Hence, a teacher serves as a role model to the students and he also creates goodwill from the perspective of the students. For a good environment, communication plays an important role in developing connection between students and teachers. A significant body of research indicates that academic achievement and student behavior are greatly influenced by the quality of the teacher and student relationship.

Teacher's non-verbal and verbal means of communication are reflected in the students' behavior, education, and ethics. Often times, it was observed that students are not quite relaxed in front of their teacher. Therefore, non-verbal communication from the teacher's side damages the character of students which might eventually result to depression.

Communication does not just happen between two persons or more spontaneously, it is a gradual step that takes place continuously. Good and effective communication can help well trained teacher to develop good relation with students¹. Thus, there is more positive

¹ Richmond, 1990 "communication in the class room: power and motivation." communication education.

relation between teachers and students². Unavailability of teachers and poor communication by teachers are the major factors that have led students to abandon their study at a certain level³. Davis (2001) proved that the self-confidence and self-ability of students helps to build their relationship with their teachers by nonverbal communication. Khan⁴, stated that the success of students is directly related to the effective communication of the teacher. Liberante ⁵opined that students and teacher relation have unlimited effect on learning, and it is very necessary for teachers to understand their students. A large amount of students agreed and thought that the friendly environment and cooperation of the teacher is an essential part of the success of the study. This research was done in Northern Border University, Saudi Arabia. Six different variables were examined and the result showed that a positive correlation was found. The friendly environment and non-verbal communication are correlated with the motivation of students. Subsequently, all these factors are important ingredients for achieving the study goals.

Conclusion

In conclusion, communication plays a very crucial role in building up the career of students. The communication of teachers, either verbal or nonverbal, is an important factor required by students to become successful in their educational pursuit. Communication motivates the students to enhance their abilities. It also encourages the students to work hard. Therefore, it is very important and necessary that the teachers should communicate with students in an effective manner.

² Baruch, Hershkovitz & P. Ang (2015). "Teacher-student Relationship and SNS-mediated 18% 64% 11% 7% Respondent enroll in University of Karachi 14 16 18 21 Education level No. of students % 14 20 18 16 72 64 18 12 11 21 8 7 Total 112 100.00 European Scientific Journal June 2018 edition Vol.14, No.16 ISSN: 1857 – 7881 (Print) e - ISSN 1857- 7431 39 Communication: Perceptions of both Role-players." Interdisciplinary Journal of e-Skills and Lifelong Learning.

³ Dinu, 2015 "Impact of Teacher-Student Communication on "High-Risk." Developing Country Studies

⁴ Khan, et al. (2017) "Communication Skills of a Teacher and Its Role in the Development of the Students' Academic Success." Journal of Education and Practice.

⁵ Liberante Lauren (2012). "The importance of teacher–student relationships, as explored through the lens of the NSW Quality Teaching Model.

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